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Design and Development of AI-Powered Smart Glasses with Integrated Cybersecurity Features for the Visually Impaired

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ABSTRACT

Visually impaired individuals face significant challenges in their daily lives, primarily due to their inability to perceive environmental obstacles. Traditional white canes offer limited spatial awareness and are inadequate for detecting objects above waist level. To address these limitations, an artificial intelligence (AI)-driven smart glasses system, enhanced with cybersecurity features, has been developed to improve environmental awareness and promote independent mobility for visually impaired users. The proposed system comprises camera modules, a battery unit, a charging dock, a custom-designed 3D-printed frame, and a dedicated mobile application. Utilizing computer vision-based AI algorithms, the system detects objects and estimates distances, providing users with real-time audio feedback for navigation. Additional functionalities include integrated GPS navigation, location sharing, and support for voice assistants, offering comprehensive guidance for daily activities. The mobile application, which operates with the smart glasses, ensures secure sharing of user location and environmental data. An AI-based threat detection mechanism has been integrated into the system architecture to enhance security, protect data privacy, and protect against unauthorized access. Security considerations are embedded in both the mobile communication infrastructure and the device's software components. In conclusion, this study presents a user-centric, technologically advanced assistive device that enhances mobility for visually impaired individuals through AI-powered perception and secure data communication.

1 INTRODUCTION

Visual impairment remains a significant challenge affecting the daily independence and safety of millions of individuals worldwide. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), over 2.2 billion people worldwide have vision impairment or blindness, severely restricting spatial perception and environmental awareness in real-world settings [1]. Traditional mobility aids such as white canes

and guide dogs offer partial solutions; however, they often fail to detect overhead or dynamic obstacles and lack integrated support for modern navigation and communication demands [2].

In recent years, advancements in artificial intelligence (AI), particularly in computer vision and machine learning, have enabled the development of assistive technologies tailored for people with disabilities [3]. Smart glasses, equipped with sensors, cameras, and AI algorithms, present a promising alternative to conventional aids by enhancing environmental understanding and offering real-time feedback. However, while functionality has significantly evolved, cybersecurity concerns related to personal data sharing, unauthorized access, and device manipulation have become increasingly critical[4].

This study introduces an AI-powered smart glasses system designed to enhance the mobility and situational awareness of visually impaired individuals. The system can detect and identify objects and integrates cybersecurity mechanisms to protect user data during communication with mobile applications and cloud systems. An AI-based threat detection layer is embedded to counter potential cyber threats, offering an end-to-end, secure assistive experience.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews related work; Section 3 details the system architecture and components; Section 4 discusses the AI and cybersecurity integration; Section 5 presents evaluation results; and Section 6 concludes the study with future research directions.

2 BACKGROUND OF THE RESEARCH

Vision plays a fundamental role in learning and guides limb and body movements. Moreover, it facilitates social interaction by enabling access to various information sources [5]. The human brain processes visual data captured by the eyes to construct a three-dimensional representation of the surrounding environment, thereby enabling individuals to acquire spatial orientation skills. However, individuals with visual impairments experience a partial or complete absence of this perceptual capability [6]. Visual impairment is a deficiency in visual information processing caused by physiological or neurological factors. Individuals with vision loss often struggle to perform daily activities because they rely on visual stimuli. Although independent mobility is a fundamental human skill, it poses serious challenges for visually impaired individuals, many of whom become dependent on others for navigation[7].

According to World Health Organization (WHO) data, approximately 2.2 billion people worldwide have vision impairment or loss. Of these, at least 1 billion have experienced vision loss due to preventable or uncorrected visual conditions [8]. These individuals often require assistance to perform routine tasks such as indoor and outdoor navigation, obstacle detection, and object recognition [9].

Visually impaired individuals face various difficulties in moving safely and independently in both indoor and outdoor environments. Due to restricted visual fields, being in an unfamiliar location or navigating open spaces becomes increasingly complex and risky [10]. Significant challenges in mobility include obstacle avoidance and navigation [11]. In recent years, technology has made significant advancements in addressing visual impairments. However, such technologies remain inaccessible to some users who rely on traditional assistive tools, such as white canes, for mobility. Nonetheless, using a cane occupies the hands and limits the ability to interact freely with the environment [6]. Moreover, canes are ineffective in detecting moving objects and obstacles at head level [12].

Daily life activities require extra effort from visually impaired individuals. To minimize such limitations, wearable technologies and assistive devices have been developed to enable safe, interactive communication with the environment. These innovative solutions support greater independence in indoor and outdoor environments, ultimately enhancing the quality of life [10-13].

Computer vision is a critical component of assistive technologies for the visually impaired. Systems based on computer vision not only enhance mobility and navigation but also contribute to object recognition and social interaction [14]. The Internet of Things (IoT) is a network of interconnected smart devices that collect and exchange data via integrated software, sensors, and

network connectivity. The healthcare sector has rapidly adopted IoT technologies, incorporating them into medical devices to improve the quality and effectiveness of care. However, increased use of such devices introduces new security vulnerabilities and risks [15]. Connected medical devices allow patients to live more normal lives and are essential. Any malfunction in these devices not only nullifies their benefits but can also pose direct harm to the patient. Consequently, numerous security regulations must be fulfilled before releasing products [16].

Implantable medical devices, in particular, utilize wireless communication technologies for applications such as treatment delivery, patient monitoring, and diagnostics. While wireless connectivity offers patients flexibility and personalized care, it simultaneously exposes the devices to cybersecurity threats [17, 18]. Common threats targeting wearable devices include data interception, unauthorized access, firmware tampering, and data leakage [19]. These cybersecurity risks can lead to severe patient harm [20], including breaches of privacy, disruptions in healthcare services, financial losses, and reputational damage [19]. According to the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA), health data have experienced significantly more privacy and security breaches than in the past two decades [21, 22].

3 EXPERIMENT AND ANALYSIS

This section presents the smart wearable system developed within the scope of the study, including its key components: the microcontroller-based smart glasses and the Flutter-based mobile application. The interactions conducted through the implemented setup, the system's operational workflow, and the functionalities provided to the user are explained in detail. The analysis focuses on evaluating the performance and usability of the integrated hardware-software architecture, highlighting the system's practical benefits and responsiveness in real-world scenarios.

3.1 Smart Glasses

The developed smart glasses capture environmental images through integrated ESP32-CAM camera modules and wirelessly transmit this data to a mobile application. The glasses are powered by a 3000 mAh battery, providing up to 4 to 5 hours of uninterrupted operation daily. The power unit, integrated into the left temple of the glasses, consists of a rechargeable battery and a TP4056 charging module. The connection between the camera modules and the power unit is designed to be easily attachable and detachable. The 3D-printed glasses frame and temples are lightweight, ergonomic, and designed to ensure efficient use of the integrated modules.

Figure 1: Prototype Smart Glasses

3.2 Mobile Application

The mobile application was developed using the Dart programming language and the Flutter Mobile UI Framework. This application enhances the overall functionality of the smart glasses, benefiting not only the user but also individuals in the user's immediate environment. It processes data from the camera module integrated into the smart glasses, enabling advanced analysis.

Using the smartphone's GPS module and the Google Maps API, the user's location is displayed on a map in real time, and a route is generated to guide the user to a designated destination. This route is communicated to the user through step-by-step navigation instructions.

The image data transferred from the smart glasses is also analyzed to detect objects and determine their distance from the user. This information is then conveyed through the mobile application interface. In this way, the system serves as an artificial visual support mechanism, helping users perceive their surroundings.

The application's operational flow is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Mobile application flow chart

The mobile application is designed with a voice assistant-supported interface to facilitate the daily lives of visually impaired individuals. Upon launching the application, users are greeted with an auditory welcome message and guided through the interface using voice commands. The main functional modules accessible via voice interaction include Map, Glasses Camera, Object Detection, and Nearby Contacts.

The Map Module provides navigation services based on the user's real-time location. When users wish to search for a specific place, they can specify the target destination via voice command or the search bar. The system calculates the optimal route between the current and target locations and delivers step-by-step navigation instructions via voice guidance.

Users can mark various locations and access features such as address information and route directions through the map interface. This module is one of the core components supporting the user's ability to move independently and safely in both indoor and outdoor environments.

Figure 3 presents the corresponding workflow diagram, and Figure 4 shows screenshots of the map section.

Figure 3 Application Map Flow Chart

Figure 4: Screenshots of the Map Section

The Glasses Camera Module is designed to analyze environmental visuals captured by the camera integrated into the smart glasses. When the user issues the voice command "Scan the Environment," the system identifies objects in the field of view and communicates their presence and distance via audio feedback. This feature is an artificial intelligence mechanism that enhances the user's environmental awareness and supports safer, more informed navigation. The module's general operational flow is illustrated in Figure 5. Screenshots of the Camera section are given in Figure 6.

Figure 5 Camera Application Flow Chart

Figure 6 Camera Section Screenshot

The Object Detection (YOLO) Module is a computer vision component that detects objects using the mobile device's camera. This module is designed to be accessible to visually impaired and non-impaired users. When the user taps the camera icon, they are directed to the image capture screen. The captured image is then processed using the YOLO (You Only Look Once) algorithm, and the detected objects are visually displayed on the screen (Fig. 7).

This functionality enables users to quickly identify objects in a given scene. As such, the Object Detection Module is one of the key components that broadens the application's appeal to a diverse user base and enhances its usability across different accessibility needs.

Figure 7: Object Detection Results

The Object Detection (TF Lite) Module provides real-time object recognition and is designed for use by both visually impaired and non-impaired individuals. Upon entering the module, the device's camera is automatically activated, and surrounding objects are analyzed and highlighted with bounding boxes. Detected objects are announced to the user via voice feedback, including the names of the identified items. If no object is recognized, the system provides an auditory warning: "No objects detected." This module is developed to enhance environmental awareness and deliver instant contextual information to the user.

The Nearby Contacts Module enables visually impaired users to add trusted individuals as “nearby” contacts within the application and share their real-time location with them. This feature is significant for ensuring user safety and enabling prompt emergency communication. Integrated into the user management system, the module enables secure, controlled location sharing. The operational flow of this module is illustrated in Figure 8.

The developed mobile application features voice-guided navigation, object detection, and location sharing, specifically designed to improve the daily lives of visually impaired individuals. Through its core modules—Map, Glasses Camera, Object Detection (TF Lite and YOLO), and Nearby Contacts—the application prioritizes both user experience and accessibility. The system has a flexible architecture that adapts to user profiles, enabling personalized interaction and improved usability. Moreover, the modular structure of the application makes it well-suited for future enhancements and expansions.

Figure 8: Nearby Contacts Module Flowchart

4 CYBERSECURITY

The smart system developed, comprising smart glasses and a mobile application, grants access to personal and sensitive data such as the user's location, image streams, and environmental perceptions. This necessitates implementing robust cybersecurity measures to ensure data privacy and prevent unauthorized access.

Various cybersecurity tests have been conducted to protect user privacy and mitigate potential malicious activities. Given that the application transmits data over network connections, a comprehensive analysis of the system's communication architecture was conducted.

The overall communication topology of the smart system is illustrated in **Figure 9**.

Figure 9: Communication System

In this context, various attack scenarios targeting unauthorized access and data manipulation were simulated on the system. Specifically, Deauthentication Attacks, Denial-of-Service (DoS) Attacks, and Man-in-the-Middle (MitM) Attacks were tested at both the web and mobile application layers.

These attacks were carried out in a controlled test environment running Kali Linux. The simulations identified and analyzed vulnerabilities in the system's network communication structure.

Figure 10 illustrates the test infrastructure, tools used, and the simulation topology in which the attacks were executed.

Figure 80 Network Topology

These security tests were conducted to evaluate the system's resilience to data security threats and plan necessary improvements to enhance protection mechanisms. The findings obtained from these tests serve as a critical guide for shaping the system's future security architecture.

To ensure the security of the smart system, a cybersecurity testing process was modeled using a five-stage flow diagram, which presents a systematic approach for identifying, detecting, and mitigating potential threats (Figure 11).

The first stage, Reconnaissance, involves identifying potential target systems on the network. Network scanning tools gather essential technical information, such as IP addresses, device brands, and models, during this phase. The target device's presence on the network is verified, and passive information-gathering activities are conducted before any attacks.

The second stage, Attack Execution, focuses on conducting direct attacks against the identified systems. In this context, standard techniques such as Denial-of-Service (DoS/DDoS), Man-in-the-Middle (MitM), and Deauthentication (Deauth Attack) were implemented to simulate real-world

security breaches. The objective is to expose vulnerabilities and analyze system behavior under threat conditions.

Figure 9: Cybersecurity Tests Flowchart

The third stage, Attack Detection, is a critical process that utilizes artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms. Machine learning models are trained to classify network traffic collected with tools such as Wireshark. These models learn to distinguish between normal and malicious traffic with high accuracy. Results indicated that the model achieved a 96.59% detection rate for MitM and DDoS attacks and an overall accuracy of 99.84%, significantly enhancing the system's early warning capability.

In the fourth stage, Monitoring, real-time traffic analysis is continuously conducted. Deep learning algorithms operate on streaming data to detect anomalies and proactively predict potential threats. This dynamic monitoring infrastructure enables the system to defend itself autonomously and respond promptly to attacks.

The final stage, Alert and Notification, is activated when an attack is detected. The system notifies the user or administrator module through visual and/or auditory alerts and automatically initiates predefined countermeasures. This ensures the system is promptly secured and restored to regular operation with minimal disruption.

5 ATTACK DETECTION

The recorded network traffic was processed through various artificial intelligence algorithms. The AI-based attacker-detection model comprises four main stages. In the first stage, raw traffic data is preprocessed before being fed into the model to improve algorithmic accuracy. During this process, the data is segmented into 10-millisecond time intervals, yielding a structured dataset suitable for analysis. In the second stage, the dataset is split into 66% for training and 34% for testing. It is then evaluated using multiple machine learning algorithms, including Naive Bayes, Neural Network, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Gradient Boosting, and k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN). A 10-fold cross-validation method is applied to ensure robust performance assessment. In the third stage, visualization techniques are employed to provide graphical interpretations of the analytical results, enabling better comparative insights across models. In the final evaluation stage, the Neural Network algorithm, which achieved the highest accuracy, F1-score, recall, and execution time performance, was selected and registered for real-time data application. This multi-phase process is illustrated in Figure 12.

Figure 12 Artificial Intelligence Application Flow Chart

The expert system used for attack detection classified captured data packets as either malicious or usual network traffic. This classification process was introduced to the expert system, with 66% of the labeled dataset employed as the training set for system learning. Once the classification process was completed, various artificial intelligence algorithms were applied to the remaining 34% validation dataset, which consisted of pre-labeled packets generated by the expert system. This evaluation aimed to test the algorithms' performance in identifying anomalies and to validate classification accuracy. As shown in Table 1, accuracy (Classification Accuracy, CA) alone is insufficient to comprehensively evaluate the performance of AI algorithms. Other metrics, such as F1-score, precision, recall, and execution time, are critical for assessing model effectiveness. The table shows that the Neural Network algorithm outperformed the others across accuracy, F1-score, precision, and recall. It demonstrated superior detection performance, making it the most suitable candidate for deployment in the expert system. Therefore, the Neural Network algorithm was selected for integration into the final attack detection architecture.

Table 1: Model Comparison

Model	Train Time (s)	Test Time (s)	CA	F1	Precision	Recall	MCC
Neural Network	1031.539	2.169	0.998	0.998	0.997	0.998	0.980
kNN	5.429	211.064	0.997	0.997	0.996	0.997	0.978
Gradient Boosting	869.254	8.246	0.997	0.997	0.997	0.997	0.976
Naive Bayes	2.015	0.641	0.912	0.926	0.944	0.912	0.288
SVM	617.537	155.716	0.423	0.559	0.946	0.423	0.144

As shown in Table 2, the system's classification accuracy at a 66% learning rate indicates its ability to correctly distinguish true positives from false positives in the test dataset. The data labeled 0 in the first row represents non-malicious (regular) network packets. The system successfully classified these normal packets with 99.9% accuracy. After analyzing 788,200 packets, it was observed that 99.9% of the regular packets were correctly identified, while only 0.1% were misclassified as malicious. In the second row, which represents actual attack packets, the system correctly identified 99.7% of them as attacks. Only 0.3% of the attack packets were incorrectly classified as benign. These values indicate that the system achieved a 99.7% detection rate for malicious traffic, with a false negative rate of 0.3%. These findings demonstrate the system's high effectiveness in detecting attack packets with minimal false classifications. The results confirm that

the system reliably distinguishes malicious from regular traffic and provides robust protection against cyber threats.

Table 1: Confusion Matrix

Actual	Predicted			Σ
	0	1	Σ	
0	%99.9	%0.1	755110	
1	%0.3	%99.7	33090	
Σ	755110	33090	788200	

6 CONCLUSION

This study presents the development of a smart glasses system and a mobile application to enhance the quality of life for visually impaired individuals. The technologies developed feature a range of features designed to help users overcome everyday challenges. In particular, functionalities such as object and human detection, location tracking, and route guidance have significantly improved users' ability to navigate independently and contributed critically to their safety. These technologies facilitate safer and more effective interaction with the environment for visually impaired individuals.

Moreover, the study offers notable contributions in the field of cybersecurity. The developed mobile application integrates an AI-based intrusion detection system to ensure the highest level of data security for its users. The application incorporates a security infrastructure capable of detecting Man-in-the-Middle (MitM) and Denial-of-Service (DoS) attacks. This system continuously monitors network traffic and data streams, instantly detecting suspicious activities and alerting users to potential threats. As a result, users' data and devices are significantly better protected against emerging cyber threats.

The findings of this study highlight meaningful pathways for integrating cybersecurity solutions into assistive technologies for the visually impaired. The inclusion of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence and machine learning not only enhances the quality of life for these individuals but also ensures the integrity and confidentiality of their data. Future work could focus on expanding the security capabilities of these systems, aiming to make threat detection mechanisms more intelligent and proactive.

Further research is recommended to examine the broader social and personal impacts of these technologies on the lives and independence of visually impaired individuals. In addition, future studies should address how AI-driven security systems can be optimized to combat more sophisticated cyber threats and identify potential limitations in large-scale deployments. Important considerations should also include the device's portability, battery life, and cost-efficiency.

In conclusion, this study represents a significant step toward developing technological solutions to improve the everyday lives of visually impaired individuals. The smart glasses and mobile application facilitate social integration and provide a secure user environment through AI-powered cybersecurity measures. Such solutions contribute not only to personal empowerment but also raise broader awareness about the importance of cybersecurity in society.

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